

Analysis of climatic factors affecting the size and efficiency of the thermal energy storage system

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Abstract: *Analysis of climatic factors affecting the size and efficiency of the thermal energy storage system.* In this paper the analysis of factors affecting the size and efficiency of the thermal energy storage system for residential building is presented. This article is focused on climatic factors. Presented results were created especially for analysis of TESSe2b system (Thermal energy storage system for energy efficient buildings. Application in domestic solar thermal systems and heat pumps) are part of the selection criteria for system devices and components. After construction of whole system, TESSe2b test application will be installed in three buildings located in the agriculture area in Austria, Cyprus and Spain.

Key words: renewable energy, energy storage, heating, cooling, climate

INTRODUCTION

The energy use in buildings has been estimated to be approximately 40% of EU total energy consumption [EU 2015]. The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) requires that all new buildings will have nearly zero-energy by the end of 2020, indicating that the low amount of energy that these buildings will require comes mostly from

renewable energy sources (RES) [EU 2012]. In addition, RES adoption is crucial if Europe is to achieve ambitious energy and emission reduction targets. TESSe2b project will enable the optimal use of renewable energy and provide one of the most advantageous solutions for correcting the mismatch that often occurs between the supply and demand of energy in residential buildings. The target of TESSe2b is to design, develop, validate and demonstrate a modular and low cost thermal storage technology in Phase Change Materials (PCM) based on solar collectors and highly efficient heat pumps for heating, cooling and domestic hot water (DHW) production. TESSe2b test application will be installed in three buildings located in the agriculture area in Austria, Cyprus and Spain. The location of one of the demonstrators is shown in Figure 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Size of each section of TESSe2b system and obtained efficiency and productivity of these sections translating into

FIGURE 1. Demonstrator localisation in the Alta Anoaia Calonge de Segarra about 100 km north-west from Barcelona (photos by T. Bakoń and from TESSe2b project homepage, <http://tesse2b.eu>)

overall system performance depend on many factors which can be divided into three main groups: climatic factors, thermal and dynamic properties of the building, and system control algorithm (the Table). This paper will discuss the influence of climatic factors.

TABLE. Factors affecting the size of the system TESSe2b

Climatic factors	The thermal and dynamic properties of a building	Technical properties of TESS system elements and control system
climate zone	the demand for heat	hydraulic system of TESSe2b
average annual air temperature	electricity supply stoppages	the system control algorithm
precipitation in Europe	the demand for domestic hot water (DHW)	technical parameters of the installation
climate zones and climate types		the location and type of temperature sensors in the TESSe2b system
average annual atmospheric temperature		factors affecting the size and efficiency of the solar heating system
average extreme air temperature		electrical energy distribution tariffs
the length of heating and cooling season		
the number of heating degree days		
the number of cooling degree days		
solar radiation potential		
wind speed and direction		

Climate zone and climate types in Europe

The allocation of the TESSe2b system is of high importance. It will determine weather conditions, i.a.: length of heating and cooling seasons, the average annual air temperature, solar radiation potential. For these reasons, depending on the location the size of each section of the TESSe2b system will vary.

The basic divisions of climate types in the world is Köppen climate classification and climate classification and regionalization by Okołowicz [1976].

The climate in Europe is affected by a number of factors, among which the most important are: the geographical location of the continent, the distance between the continent and seas and oceans, and vertical landform. The latitude is related to land surface insolation, the length of day and night, and indirectly the temperature distribution, the type of soil and vegetation. The proximity of the seas and oceans affects wind direction, air temperature and humidity. On the southern edge of Europe, the longest day of summer is about 14 h 30 min. On the northern edges the polar day including the civil twilight dusk and dawn lasts several months. Variation in the duration of day and night has an impact on air temperature, humidity evaporation and the vegetation of the organic world. The climate in Europe is significantly affected by air masses, especially coming from the Atlantic, and continental air masses coming from Asia. The Gulf Stream flowing along the coast causes deflection of heat reaching +5°C at 50° N, +8°C at 60° W and about +12°C at

70° W. Due to the “heating” of Europe by the Gulf Stream, the port of Murmansk, located in the furthest north of the continent, does not freeze over the year. The influence of oceanic air masses is noticeable in Western Europe in the winter. In turn, on the eastern edge of the continent, the influences the Asian continental air are dominant Europe distinctive landform, especially the lack of high mountains in the meridional layout favors the penetration of the Europe area by oceanic or continental air masses. The continent vertical landform determines local variation of the climate, expressed clearly in the floor system climate phenomena in the mountains. With the increase of the height, drop in air temperatures is noticeable. Dry air rising up of for every 100 m, and the air saturated with humidity cools down by average maximal 0.5°C per 100 m. Most of the area of Europe lies in the temperate zone and is covered by all characteristic types of climate – oceanic, continental and temperate – in both hot and cold subzone. In the temperate zone of the average annual temperature ranges from 0 to 10°C, while the temperature of the warmest month exceeds 10°C. In the northern parts of Europe, there is a circumpolar zone, where the temperature of the warmest month is below 10°C. In the circumpolar zone there is very little rainfall throughout a year. In the southern part of the continent there is a subtropical zone with an average annual temperature from 10° to 20°C. In Europe, there are generally five types of climates: dry, humid temperature, humid cold, cold polar and high-land climate.

The air temperatures in Europe

Distribution of air temperature in Europe shows significant differences between winter and summer. The meridional system is represented on the map of Europe showing the distribution of air temperature in January (Fig. 2 on the left) – the farther from the Atlantic Ocean the colder, which is validated by warming effect of sea air in the winter. An important role is also played by the warm Gulf Stream, which warms even the northern coast of the Scandinavian Peninsula. The map of Europe showing the distribution of air temperature in July (Fig. 2 on the right), the temperature distribution becomes parallel in shape. This is mainly related with the insolation, depending on latitude.

The average annual air temperatures show that in the south-western part of Europe (low latitude and proximity to the ocean), the average annual temperature is much higher above 10°C than in the north-eastern part, where the average annual temperature is below 0°C (high

latitude and significant distance from the Atlantic). This means that in the south-western part of Europe the heating season will be much shorter than in the north-eastern part. In the south-western part the leading role in the heat supply to the TESSe2b system will lie with the solar heating system, a heat pump will mostly work in reversible mode providing cooling to the building. In the north-western part of Europe, the heating season will last much longer, which means that the priority role in meeting the heat demand of the TESSe2b system will lie with a heat pump compressor. The significance of the solar heating system will be negligible.

Precipitation in Europe

Precipitation in Europe are concentrated in the western part of the continent (Fig. 3). This is due, of course, to the proximity of the Atlantic Ocean. The highest annual totals (over 2,000 mm) are recorded in the Alpine region (western slopes), where the formation

FIGURE 2. The air temperature in Europe in January and July

Source: Wiking homepage, <http://www.wiking.edu.pl>.

FIGURE 3. Precipitation in Europe throughout the year
Source: As in Figure 2.

of rainfall is also fueled by an increase in altitude. In contrast, the driest areas are steppes of the Caspian Lowland and islands of the Arctic Ocean, where precipitation throughout the year is less than 200 mm. Comparing the distribution of precipitation in January and July one can notice that most of the precipitation in Europe comes in summer. Generally, this translates to that the hot (humid) air is more prone to condensation (easier to be cooled) than the cold air. Reverse situation – dry summers and moist winters – are found only in the southern part of the continent, i.e. along the coastline of the Mediterranean Sea. This is related to movement of tropical highs over this area in summer and mid-latitude lows in the winter. Moreover, in Europe there are

areas with more or less even distribution of precipitation during the year, e.g. the Atlantic islands and coastlines (heavy rain fall), the Arctic islands and Caspian steppes (light rain fall).

Temperate maritime climate is predominant in almost all Western Europe. It is characterized by small temperature amplitudes throughout a year (a few degrees in °C) and relatively heavy, all-year long precipitation (~1,000 mm). In the hot subzone temperatures are higher by average of 5°C than in the cold subzone. Temperate continental climate is predominant in Eastern Europe (mainly Russia and Ukraine). Recorded temperatures indicate large amplitudes over a year, e.g. 30°C in Moscow. Precipitation rarely exceeds 500 mm and occurs

mostly in summer. Winters are long and harsh (especially in the cold subzone), and summers tend to be hot (in the hot subzone). Temperate climate – characterizes Central Europe (hot subzone) and most of the Scandinavian Peninsula (cold subzone). It has combines characteristics of oceanic and continental type. In subsequent years, depending on the dominant air circulation, a preponderance of oceanic or continental influence is noticeable. Subarctic climate – polar and subpolar – are characterized by extremely low temperatures and low levels of precipitation. However, in Europe, temperatures are not so very low (as in Asia or Antarctica), because the influence of the warm Gulf Stream reaches far beyond the Arctic Circle.

Humid subtropical climate – is also called Mediterranean climate, since the area of the Mediterranean Sea is typical of its occurrence. It is characterized by long, hot, dry summers and short, mild, rainy winters. Besides, in a small area within the Iberian Peninsula, the climate is dry subtropical. It differs primarily from the humid in precipitation which does not exceed 500 mm per year here. Alpine climate – includes climates of the temperate and subtropical area. In each case the increase in height above sea level causes a decrease in temperature and increase in rainfall. This is shown by example of the Alps, Pyrenees, Carpathians, Scandinavian Mountains, Dynarskie.

The average annual atmospheric temperature

Ambient temperature is variable within the time frame of a day, a month and a year. It should be noted that change in ambient air temperature occurring within a day, month or year is not linear for particular location. This means that the demand for heat and cold during a day, month and year for the specific location will also vary. What can have the biggest impact on the thermal comfort of the TESSe2b system user are daily ambient temperatures, especially if the system is located in Eastern Europe. In Poland, in transition periods of autumn–winter and winter–spring in particular temperatures within 24 h can vary in the range of 0°–15°C. The impact of such 24-hour temperature gradient over the indoor temperature is mainly dependent on the dynamic properties of the building which is largely affected by the material used for building insulation. That

means a building with lower heat loss coefficient will have much longer time constant and thus will be less sensitive to daily changes in ambient temperature than a building with higher heat loss coefficient, and thus the shorter time constant. This means that in case of installation of the TESSe2b system in the building with short time constant, daily atmospheric temperature changes must be countered by the TESSe2b automatic control system, which should make the appropriate adjustments of temperature set in heating circuit (circuits) in order to maintain thermal comfort of the users.

The other factor with significant impact on the 24-hour temperature pattern is cloud cover. This means that the daily temperature changes can also affect the TESSe2b system installed in the building with a short time constant located in central, southern or western Europe. Knowing the gradient of daily temperature changes and average daily temperature in a given location is essential for the TESSe2b control system to determine the dynamic properties of the building in which it is installed.

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Average monthly air temperature has little effect on the TESSe2b control system, but it significantly affects the estimation of the size of individual sections of the TESSe2b system (Fig. 4). Knowing the average monthly temperature enables to estimate the length of periods in which the demand for heat and the demand for cooling occur exclusively, and the

FIGURE 4. Examples of average monthly waveforms of air temperature in Poland

Source: Start homepage, <http://start24.blogspot.com/2012/09/klimat-polski-jaka-powinna-byc-dzis.html>.

periods in which they occur simultaneously. More detailed information is provided by the degree days analysis.

The average annual air temperature has a negligible effect on the configuration and adjustment of the TESSe2b system. It only provides general information about climate conditions in a given location.

Average extreme air temperature

Average extreme air temperature (the basis for dimensioning heat transfer devices) is calculated as the mean value of the lowest and highest temperatures recorded within multi-year period. It should be noted that extreme average air temperature in the winter in centre of city is higher by 2–4 K and in the summer – by 1–2 K than at the periphery. Furthermore, the mean value of the extreme temperature depends on the type of building (detached, semi-detached, ribbon development, building atrium).

Average extreme air temperature should be a key design parameter for TESSe2b system heat receivers, because – as any heating and cooling system – the TESSe2b should be designed for the most adverse conditions. Therefore, in order to properly design the TESSe2b system it is necessary to determine the average extreme temperature for both the heating and cooling season in a given location.

The length of heating and cooling season

The length of heating and cooling season is a factor with less importance for the size and selection of TESSe2b system components. A period within a calendar year in which the average daily air temperature drops below 15°C is considered the beginning and at the same time the end of the heating season. The beginning and at the same time the end of the cooling season is marked by a period in

which the average daily air temperature is higher than 20°C.

However, length of heating season in a single location can vary within certain limits. For newly built well-insulated structures the length of heating and cooling season may be shortened because of much lower demand for heat and cooling than in case of an existing building with worse insulation and consequently greater heat loss. One may assume that the heating season in low-energy building would begin even with the average daily air temperature drop below 12°C, and the cooling season with the average daily air temperature rising above 23°C. In all cases considered it has to be assumed that the average temperature in the building is 20°C.

The length of the heating and cooling season depends on the location and impacts the amount of electric energy consumed to drive the heat pump compressor and circulation pumps of the TESSe2b hydraulic system. It also has a significant impact on the size of PCM heat and cold storage, as well as the temperature level in ground heat exchanger which is a ground energy source for heat pump. For locations with cooling season much longer than the heating season the PCM tank for cold storage should be of significantly greater capacity than the PCM tank for heat storage. For location with heating season much longer than cooling season the PCM tank for heat storage should be of much greater capacity than the PCM tank for cold storage. In order to estimate the size of the TESSe2b heating and cooling storage systems in a given location, it is necessary to determine the length of the heating and cooling season.

The number of heating and cooling degree days

The number of degree days which relates mainly to the heating season is an important parameter which allowing i.a. a comparison of heat consumption for TESSe2b systems in different locations (Fig. 5 on the left). The number of degree days is calculated by multiplying the number of heating days per year and the difference between the average temperature of heated room and average outdoor temperature during that year.

This provides the climate “image” for location where the TESSe2b system is installed. With monthly or hourly data, it is possible to perform more accurate analysis to estimate the number of days and the demand for heat and cooling for the TESSe2b system per year.

When used in the system TESSe2b as receivers heating and cooling ventilation equipment, e.g.: fan coils, especially in the case of system location TESSe2b in hot climates, where within a year prevails operation of the TESSe2b system cooling, very important from the point of operation of the system is to determine the number of degree hours for cooling, which is the product of the number of hours when the system works in the cooling mode and the difference between the average temperature of the outside air and the necessary air supply temperature. Analyzing the number of degree hours of cooling (Fig. 5 on the right), it is important to refer degree hours to times of day, because depending on the time of day the outside temperature and cooling demand is changing. In the case of TESSe2b system location, which is required for continuous operation in the

FIGURE 5. Number of heating and cooling degree hours

Source: Eurostat homepage, <http://ec.europa.eu>.

cooling mode, can be use the monthly analyzes.

Solar radiation potential

The potential of solar radiation has a big impact on the size of TESSe2b respective sections and operating the system. Solar radiation is an additional source of heat, however, of very high variability. Through examining general availability of solar radiation throughout the year, it becomes evident that the lowest solar energy potential comes with winter period, when the sun is in the lowest position above the horizon, while the highest solar energy potential comes with summer period, when the sun is in the highest position above the horizon. Depending on the location of the

TESSe2b system (northern vs. southern Europe) the duration of the winter and summer periods is significantly different which relates directly to the duration of the heating and cooling season and to average daily, monthly and annual temperature (Fig. 6).

Thermal load of the building, which results from the heat demand can be covered in certain periods (longer or shorter depending on location) through available solar energy. However, to a large extent covering the thermal load of the building (heat gain) depend on the structure position against the north-south direction, architecture, shading and technical condition of a building.

In case of a building with decent thermal insulation and heat-insulating windows heat gain from solar radiation

FIGURE 6. Global horizontal irradiation

Source: Solargis homepage, <http://solargis.info>.

(which accounts for the system cooling load) will be much higher than for older buildings with poor thermal insulation. Therefore, designing the TESSe2b system in two buildings with different thermal properties in the same location the TESSe2b system in a building with better thermal properties must be optimized to operate in cooling mode more frequently than in case of a building with bigger heat loss, for which the TESSe2b system must be optimized to operate for more frequent use of heating mode.

Building architecture also has significant impact on the heat gain from solar radiation. Modern architecture has trended towards the increase of the window surface in the building. Currently, buildings are designed, where the share of window surface in the wall area amounts to more than 50%. From the design and

the TESSe2b system operation perspective the share of window surface in the wall area is essential. Glass surfaces cause an increase in building heat loss in winter period and significant heat gain in the winter and summer period.

By analyzing the size of the TESSe2b system respective sections and its operational mode, one must remember that in the winter and transition periods, heat gain from solar radiation come from the south side, while in the summer period – from the east and west side of the building. For this reason, in buildings with a high window-to-wall area ratio (WWR) it is very important to perform preliminary analyses on the orientation of the building and, to be more precise, the orientation of window surfaces. Also to be take into account (as already pointed out) the construction of the building. In

light-frame structures with poor thermal insulation heat accumulation will be significantly reduced due to low heat capacity compared to heavy-frame structures (thick walls), but the process of heating process in light-frame structure will be much faster due to a shorter time constant and indoor temperatures achieved will be much higher than in case of heavy-frame structure, which has a much larger heat capacity and also a longer time constant.

The color of the wall surface and roof of the building in which the TESSE2b system will be installed should also be brought to attention while analyzing the impact of solar irradiance on the system. Due to the lack of reflection dark surfaces reach a much higher temperature in summer than the bright or glossy surfaces.

Summing up, in order to properly design the TESSE2b system in an existing building and develop an algorithm for the system control, significant periods and doses of solar radiation must be collated month by month and annually as well as the actual building heat gain sourced from solar radiation. The problem in estimating the exact value of average solar irradiance doses and heat gain from solar radiation is about large fluctuations, both location and season dependent. Hence mean values must be used in calculations.

Insolation defined as the number of sunshine hours or the number of hours in which the rays of the Sun strike the surface of the Earth directly is an important parameter that allows calculation of the number of the solar pump operating hours in the solar panel system. This parameter is quite essential because unlike

solar radiation potential ($\text{kWh}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) but describes weather (climatic) conditions. Climatic conditions described by insolation determine the possibility of utilizing solar energy and limit the cost-effective life of a solar heating system.

Wind speed and direction

Wind is an important meteorological factor significantly affecting the heat demand of the building. In winter, the temperature difference between the inside and outside of the building is high which creates a pressure differential and as a result a negative pressure due to which the cold outdoor air is sucked into the interior through leaks in the outer shell of the building (doors, windows, etc.). Therefore, when calculating the size of the TESSE2b system section not only it is important to determine the heat and cooling demand resulting from building construction but also to consider the location of the building in relation to how wind direction is distributed (wind rose) and in relation to other buildings. West wind is most common in central and eastern Europe.

The heat and cooling demand for the same building will be different for each of the following locations: in a rural area open space, within terraced structure with edge location of the building for which the TESSE2b system is designed, within the same structure but with the building located in the middle and in an urban area. Thus, both monthly and annual analysis of wind speeds in given location becomes essential. Usually the average wind speed is much higher in winter than summer in central and eastern Europe. Also the recorded wind

speeds are higher in coastal than inland. Consequently there will be higher heat demand for a building located in the coastal area than for inland location. The average wind speed at a given location is also a key factor.

CONCLUSIONS

In the design of TESSe2b system the analysis of the climatic factors is very substantial for its size and efficiency. The presented analysis shows that the location of the TESSe2b system will determine the size of each of its components. The following factors will have significant impact: the average annual atmospheric temperature, the average extreme air temperature, the length of both – the heating and cooling season, the number of heating and cooling degree days, energy resources of solar radiation, insolation, wind speed and direction, all of which are discussed in the following sections. The practical application of in this article presented analysis has found place by the preparation of database containing usage profiles linked to climate and building type, which contains over 300 predefined locations in several European countries and is used to select elements of the TESSe2b system based on among others localization, climatic factors, building type and preselected components (solar collectors, heat pumps, etc.). The database was one of the deliverables provided by the TESSe2b project realization and will be use for the TESSe2b system size and efficiency calculation.

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Streszczenie: *Analiza czynników klimatycznych wpływających na wielkość i sprawność systemu magazynowania energii cieplnej.* W artykule przedstawiono analizę czynników wpływających na wielkość i sprawność systemu magazynowania energii cieplnej budynku mieszkalnego. W tej publikacji skupiono się na czynnikach klimatycznych. Przedstawiona analiza została wykonana dla systemu TESSe2b (Ciepły system magazynowania energii dla budynków energooszczędnych. Zastosowany w domowych instalacjach solarnych i z pompami ciepła) i stanowi część kryteriów wyboru urządzeń i komponentów systemowych. Po zakończeniu budowy całego systemu, pilotażowe instalacje z systemem TESSe2b zostaną zainstalowane i przetestowane w trzech budynkach zlokalizowanych na obszarach wiejskich w Austrii, na Cyprze i w Hiszpanii.

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